

A Multidisciplinary Approach to Linking Seismological Observations and Environmental Processes

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Key Points:

- River discharge, wind and boat drive identifiable and distinct seismic signatures on the lake bed.
- Ocean bottom seismometers (OBS) capture signals related to the abrupt thermal shift in the water body on the lake bed.
- Wind-driven lake microseisms are clearly identified at periods shorter than 2 s.

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Abstract

Attributing seismic signals to specific environmental processes remains a fundamental and evolving challenge in environmental seismology. The dynamical response of lakes to environmental and man-made forcings such as strong winds, river discharge, flooding and boat disturbances offers a valuable opportunity for monitoring these phenomena using ocean bottom seismometers (OBS). However, the assignment of seismic signals to events beyond well-characterized sources such as earthquakes or explosions remains a challenge in traditional seismology. We use a multidisciplinary approach that integrates diverse observational datasets to establish associations between environmental events and their corresponding seismic signatures. We conducted an experiment around the Muota Delta in Lake Lucerne using ocean bottom seismometers, Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP), and thermistors together with permanent limnological and meteorological nearby measuring stations. This study establishes the first comprehensive catalog characterizing seismic response at the lake floor to diverse environmental forcings. Our result reveals that the atmospheric-forcing induced seismic signature observed in two distinct period bands: above 10 s, and between 0.4 and 2 s. River discharge-driven seismic signals are characterized by longer periods (≥ 25 s). Finally, boat-induced pressure and seismic signals exhibit harmonic oscillations with periods between 10 and 100 s. This study opens new horizons in environmental seismology, demonstrating the potential of ocean bottom seismometers for monitoring various environmental processes when installed on the lake floor.

Plain Language Summary

We present lacustrine seismic signals associated with environmental processes by combining data from weather measurements, hydrodynamic observations, limnological monitoring, and seismological recordings using ocean bottom seismometers (OBSs). The OBSs, deployed on the lakebed, act as sensitive “ears” that listen to the lake’s interior, but cannot distinguish the signal origin or source. In lacustrine-like marine environments, interactions with weather conditions, such as wind and discharge forcing induce seismic signals at the lake-bottom station, that are likely less pronounced at terrestrial seismic stations. This integrated approach improves our understanding of how natural environmental dynamics can be monitored using seismometers and/or hydrophones.

1 Introduction

Environmental seismology aims to study mechanical vibrations caused by external sources—i.e., those outside the solid Earth, including the coupling between the solid Earth and the atmosphere, hydrosphere, and cryosphere (Larose et al., 2015). It is based on the analysis of seismic signals to gain insight into the environmental processes and their dynamics. Seismic signals, including ambient seismic noise, are recorded using both conventional instruments, such as land-based and ocean bottom seismometers and emerging technologies, including Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and Mobile Earthquake Recording in Marine Areas by Independent Divers (Simons et al., 2009; Lindsey et al., 2017). Meteorological and hydrological services routinely monitor environmental variables such as strong winds, rainfall, temperature, atmospheric pressure, floods, and variations in ocean

63 and lake levels. In the context of environmental seismology, these external observations
64 are essential for interpreting seismic signals, as environmental forcing can significantly in-
65 fluence seismic recordings. Broadband seismometers record a wide range of geophysical,
66 anthropogenic, and environmental processes. However, such a broad sensitivity make it
67 challenging to unambiguously associate specific non-conventional seismic signals, those not
68 linked to well-characterized sources (e.g., earthquakes, explosions) with specific environmen-
69 tal events. Therefore, a multidisciplinary approach integrating seismological, meteorological,
70 limnological, and hydrological observations is crucial for reliably correlating environmental
71 processes with seismic signatures. Analyzing such integrated datasets will enhance our abil-
72 ity to characterize environmental seismic signatures, and ultimately lead to more accurate
73 and efficient monitoring using seismic instrumentation.

74 Recent studies have shown the potential of geophysical observations for monitoring
75 processes occurring in the marine environment such as submarine landslide (Hampton et
76 al., 1996; Lin et al., 2010; Clare et al., 2024), tidal effect (La Forgia et al., 2023), seiches
77 (McGarr, 1965), foehn-like strong wind (Wamba et al., 2025), and sediment transport (Hage
78 et al., 2024). Submarine landslide and sediment transport can be damaging to offshore
79 infrastructure, including communication cables (Pope et al., 2017). Lakes serve as ideal
80 testbeds for studying these processes, with results transferable to oceanic settings. This
81 study focuses on an experiment conducted in Lake Lucerne (Switzerland), using weather
82 stations, ocean bottom seismometers, geological gauges, and hydrodynamic measurements
83 to link environmental events, such as river discharge, strong wind, and boat navigation
84 with specific seismic signatures. This study aims to illustrate the diversity of processes that
85 can be observed with ocean bottom seismometers (OBSs) installed at the lake bed and to
86 emphasize their potential for real-time monitoring of near-surface environmental events.

87 **2 Study site and dataset**

88 **2.1 Study Site**

89 Lake Lucerne (Fig. 1b) is a fjord-type, perialpine lake of glacial origin, composed of
90 several elongated basins (Hilbe et al., 2011). Its average depth is approximately 104 m. The
91 study area is located in the southernmost basin, known as the Uri Basin, which lies in a
92 rectilinear valley with steep slopes that form a natural wind channel (Fig. 1b). The basin
93 reaches a maximum water depth of about 199 m (Hilbe & Anselmetti, 2014). The Muota
94 River is one of the main inflows supplying water to the lake.

95 The lake has experienced tsunami events in the past (Hilbe & Anselmetti, 2014, 2015).
96 Several permanent monitoring stations are collecting long-term measurements at this alpine
97 study site (Fig. 1). A hydrological gauging station is monitoring river discharge. In the
98 north, at Brunnen, a digital limnograph monitors the lake level. The seismic land-based
99 station MUO, located ~ 2 km east of the lake, continuously records seismic activity in the
100 region. A weather station is located in Altdorf, at the southern end of the basin. The
101 bathymetric map was used to effectively optimize the deployment of five ocean bottom
102 seismometers for our experiment (Fig. 1), indicated by red dots in Fig. 1c. The positions
103 of three OBSs were changed during the experiment, which explains the apparent total
104 of eight OBSs in Fig. 1c. Horizontal anchors (Fig. 1d) were used during deployment to

105 optimize the coupling between the lake floor and ocean bottom seismometers (OBS). For
 106 each OBS, a hydrophone (pressure sensor) is mounted on top (Fig. 1d). Data derived from
 107 the instruments installed at the site of our study are described in Section 2.2.

108 **2.2 Dataset**

109 Our multidisciplinary approach integrates data from our temporary experiment and
 110 from permanent stations.

111 **2.2.1 Datasets from permanent monitoring stations**

112 Meteorological, hydrodynamic, onshore seismological, and limnological data are recorded
 113 continuously and permanently. The meteorological data include wind speed, wind direction,
 114 air temperature, and atmospheric pressure measured at the meteorological station located in
 115 the southern part of the basin, in Altdorf, and maintained by the Swiss Meteorological Ser-
 116 vice (MeteoSwiss). The limnological and hydrodynamic data correspond to the lake level (in
 117 meters above sea level; m a.s.l.) and the river discharge, recorded by the digital limnograph
 118 at Brunnen and the hydrological gauging station at Muota, respectively. Both datasets are
 119 provided by the Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN). All the above measurements
 120 are time-averaged using a 10-minute sampling window. The land-based seismometer (MUO)
 121 is an STS-2 model equipped with a Centaur digitizer and is part of the permanent network
 122 (CH) of the Swiss Seismological Service. Its characteristics are similar to those of the OBSs,
 123 namely high-gain broadband sensors described below. Temporary seismological and hydro-
 124 dynamic stations deployed during the experiments conducted in Lake Lucerne (Fig. 1a-c)
 125 are detailed below.

126 **2.2.2 Seismological dataset from temporary seismic stations**

127 The seismological data were acquired using five NAMU ocean bottom seismometers
 128 instrumented with Trillium Compact 120 s (K.U.M. Offshore GmbH), high-gain, broadband
 129 sensors that were deployed in the lake at water depths of ~ 40 – 73 m, northern of the inflow
 130 of the Muota between July 2023 and May 2024. The data were recorded with a sampling
 131 rate of 250 Hz. These OBS were also equipped with hydrophones (HTI-04-PCA ULF) that
 132 are mounted directly on the frame of the OBS (Fig. 1d). Sampling rate of the hydrophone
 133 data is also 250 Hz. In December 2024, three OBSs (MUS08, MUS09, and MUS10) were
 134 repositioned to a new location until final recovery. After their recovery, clock drifts quantified
 135 as the difference between the internal clock and the GPS-signal (skew) was corrected using
 136 the method developed by Hannemann et al. (2014). For data validation lacustrine seismic
 137 signals from the OBSs were further compared with those recorded by land-based seismometer
 138 MUO. For each event, we analyzed the seismic signal from the OBS exhibiting the stronger
 139 records, rather than considering data from all stations. Consequently, we focus on stations
 140 MUS03 and MUS05 for environmental events, and MUS08 for noise.

Figure 1: (a) Map of Switzerland indicating the location of Lake Lucerne. (b) Map of Lake Lucerne showing the Muota River discharging into the lake. (c) Zoomed-in view of Alpine Lake Lucerne showing the bathymetry and the locations of ocean bottom seismometers (OBSs), indicated by red dots. The two ADCP moorings are indicated as ADCP-01 and ADCP-02. (d) The frame of the Ocean Bottom Seismometer shows the pressure sensor (hydrophone) and the anchor supporting the mounted seismometer. (e) Sketch of the ADCP mooring system showing the installation of the ADCP in the water column. The water depth at the ADCP mooring site is 114 m.

2.2.3 Hydrodynamic dataset from temporary moorings

The hydrodynamical data are acquired using two moorings that were placed within the subaqueous continuation of the Muota inflow. Both moorings are equipped with an up-ward and down-ward looking Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) positioned 23 m and 23.9 m above the lake floor respectively (Fig. 1e). The water depth at the ADCP mooring site is 114 m. Both ADCP are Teledyne RD Instruments (RDI) models operating at frequencies of 1200 kHz and 600 kHz respectively. Mooring 1 (ADCP-01) failed during the experiment, whereas Mooring 2 (ADCP-02) operated successfully. However, thermistor-based temperature measurements along Mooring 1 (ADCP-01) were still successful. The downward-looking ADCP collects data in 25 vertical bins with a 1 m resolution (bin sizes), while the upward-looking profiler uses 30 bins with a 2 m resolution. The ADCP operates based on the Doppler principle, emitting acoustic pulses (pings) and measuring frequency shifts in the returning echoes caused by particles or organisms suspended in the moving water. The measured frequency shifts are used by the instrument to determine current velocity, flow direction, and acoustic backscatter (used as a proxy for suspended particles) at various depths within the water column. Like the meteorological and limnological measurements, the hydrodynamical measurements are time-averaged over a 10-minute sampling window. This sampling interval effectively reduces potential noise in the data.

3 Methods

We combine data from specifically deployed devices with meteorological, hydrological, and limnological observations acquired from Swiss local agencies. Temporal references for all datasets are standardized to Coordinated Universal Time (UTC). Our analysis focuses on the vertical component of the seismic signals, along with additional hydrodynamic and/or meteorological measurements. Seismic waveforms, hydrological, and meteorological observations are routinely integrated and jointly visualized to facilitate the identification of seismic signals associated with environmental processes. For each environmental event, such as high river discharge or strong wind, we restricted the analysis to the event day (i.e., 24 hours), to avoid associating other processes with its seismic signature, as the ultimate goal is to capture the instantaneous environmental processes using OBS. We acknowledge that some processes in the chain, as well as preconditioning processes or conditions, may be disregarded. Nevertheless, our priority remains the detection of instantaneous processes, due to our objective of advancing toward real-time monitoring.

To gain insight into the temporal and frequency characteristics of the environmental processes that induce seismic signals, we followed a three-step approach: (1) we analyzed the time series of environmental and seismological observations; (2) we analyzed the spectrogram and/or power spectral density (PSD) of the seismological records to identify the frequency bands associated with the environmental process; and (3) we compared the pressure signal with the hydrodynamic records. At each step, when necessary to better distinguish between lacustrine and terrestrial signals, we compared the observations from the ocean bottom seismometer with those from the land-based station.

4 Results

4.1 Validation of OBS data and investigation of short-period lacustrine processes

To assess the reliability of the ocean bottom seismometer (OBS) recordings, we compared their signals with those from a nearby land-based station (MUO) during both seismic event and quiescent periods. An earthquake of moment magnitude (M_w) 7.5 that occurred in Japan on 1 January 2024 provided a clear reference event. The waveforms were consistently recorded by the OBS deployed in Lake Lucerne and the adjacent land-based station (MUO), indicating good data quality and stable instrument performance (Fig. 2a,c). The short duration of the signal and the clear separation of seismic phases (e.g., body and surface waves) facilitated its distinction from signals driven by environmental processes.

Figure 2: Example of the M_w 7.5 earthquake that occurred in Japan on January 1, 2024, and observed in Lake Lucerne during the experiment. (a) Seismic waveform recorded on the vertical component of the OBS (MUS05). (b) Spectrogram of the OBS vertical-component seismogram. (c) Seismic waveform recorded on the vertical component of the land-based station MUO. (d) Daily spectrogram of the MUO vertical-component seismogram.

The earthquake generated a broadband frequency spectrum with a high-energy in the entire period band around 07:12 (Fig. 2b,d). These observations demonstrate that the OBS effectively records seismic events while also capturing additional short-period (< 1 s) high-energy signals from non-seismic lake processes. These signals are absent at land-based stations. The passage of seismic waves through the lake did not appear to trigger any secondary hydrodynamic responses, as no variations were observed in key parameters such as temperature, current velocity, or direction (Fig. S1c,e-f). In addition, no significant evidence of sediment resuspension, often associated with water-column heterogeneity (defined as backscatter perturbation, e.g. Wamba et al., 2025), was observed during or after the earthquake (Fig. S1d).

202 We then identified a calm day (13 January 2024) with no notable events such as earth-
 203 quakes, strong winds, or high river discharge (Fig. S2), and compared the power spectral
 204 density (PSD) throughout the day (Fig. 3). The PSD of signals from both the ocean bot-
 205 tom seismometer (MUS08) and the land-based station (MUO) exhibited variability at short
 206 periods (between 0.1 and 1 s). In this period band, the seismic energy at the OBS exceeds
 207 that of the land-based station by ~ 40 dB, consistent with the observations shown in Fig. 2.
 208 The variability in the PSD within this short-period range revealed a peak at around 0.4 s
 209 (2.5 Hz) in both spectra (Fig. 3a,b). This 0.4 s peak corresponds to lake microseisms, whose
 210 characteristics are influenced by the lake’s geometry and size (Xu et al., 2017; Carchedi et
 211 al., 2022; Farrell et al., 2023; Besedina et al., 2024).

212 At longer period, the PSDs display a peak at approximately 5 s period, for both the
 213 OBS and the land-based station. This peak is characteristic of the secondary ocean micro-
 214 seisms (SOM) and originate from ocean wave interactions, either the Atlantic Ocean or the
 215 Mediterranean Sea (e.g. Stutzmann et al., 2009). The SOM exhibits a similar shape in the
 216 period range 3–10 s and the same maximum amplitude of -135 dB on the lakebed OBS and
 on the land stations.

Figure 3: Power spectral density (PSD) for a calm day (January 13, 2024), expressed in decibels ($10 \log_{10}(\text{m}^2/\text{s}^4/\text{Hz})$). (a) PSD of the noise recorded on the vertical component of the ocean bottom seismometer MUS08. (b) PSD of the noise recorded on the vertical component of the land-based station MUO. The gray curves represent the new high noise model (NHNM) and new low noise model (NLNM) from *Peterson, 1993*.

217

218 Above 15 s period, the power spectral density variability is less pronounced at the land-
 219 based station than at the OBS. At even longer periods (> 30 s), the energy level at the
 220 land-based station approaches the global low-noise model threshold, indicating the overall
 221 quietness of the terrestrial site. At these same periods, the lakebed OBS displays a PSD
 222 increase and larger variability, that might be related to lake activities.

4.2 Seismic signal induced by river discharge

On 22 September 2023, large rainfall led to an increase in river discharge (Fig. 4a,b). Precipitation persisted for approximately seven hours prior to the abrupt rise in the river discharge (Fig. 4) from 20 to 80 m³/s, a 4-fold increase over a short time period, likely in response to rainfall event. Fig. 4c shows the seismic signal band-pass filtered between 25 and 120 s, while the associated spectrogram (Fig. 4d) corresponds to the unfiltered signal (shown on Fig. S3). The filtered signal exhibits higher amplitudes during discharge, within the time window of ~07:12–12:00, in contrast to the lower amplitudes observed before and after discharge. The choice of the period band is guided by the spectrogram and power spectral density analysis of the seismic signal. The onset of the filtered seismic signal recorded by the OBS coincides with the abrupt increase in discharge, suggesting that the instrument responded to the lake–inflow interaction.

In order to better characterize the seismic signature of the river discharge, a comparative analysis of the power spectral densities (PSDs) of the seismic signal from the OBS and the land-based station is performed. The power spectral densities (PSDs) are computed in three distinct time windows: prior to the river discharge (00:00–02:00), during the discharge event (07:00–12:00) and after the discharge (21:00–23:00). The pre- and post-discharge windows (Fig. 5a,c,d,f) reveal seismic noise at both stations, with seismic energy falling between the global new low and high seismic noise models, respectively called NLNM and NHNM. The presence of short-period (≤ 0.2 s), high-energy spectral content in the power spectral densities before, during, and after the discharge (Fig. 5a-c), as well as in the spectrogram (Fig. 4d) of the OBS seismic signal, is likely driven by lake-related processes. Both the OBS and the land-based station exhibit a peak at 0.4 s (2.5 Hz) in their power spectral densities, which becomes more pronounced after the discharge event (Fig. 5c,f) and is consistent with the peak observed during the quiet day, associated with lake microseisms (Fig. 3). The seismic energy peak observed at a period of ~ 5 s (Fig. 5), at both the land-based station and the OBS corresponds to secondary ocean microseisms (SOM) unrelated to lacustrine processes. During the discharge period (07:00–12:00), the OBS recorded elevated seismic energy exceeding the NHNM, for periods longer than 25 s (Fig. 5b), while the land-based station (MUO) remained relatively quiet, with seismic energy close to the NLNM (Fig. 5e). This demonstrates the interest of OBSs at the lakebed, which record high PSD with large variability related to the river discharge that are not detected by the land station. This analysis allows a clearer distinction between the period band of the river-discharge-induced signal (above 25 s) and that of the lake microseisms (below 2 s), as shown in Fig. 5.

The lake’s response to river discharge is not limited to the observed seismic signal. Associated hydrodynamic changes are observed within the lake system. Among these, the rise in lake level—defined as the vertical height of the water surface above a reference point—was likely induced by rainfall and increased river discharge (Fig. 6a). This increase in lake level likely induced the rise in hydrostatic pressure, given the linear relationship between the two metrics (Fig. 6a). The hydrophone also recorded an acoustic signal whose onset broadly coincides with that of the seismic signal when filtered in the period band 25–120 s (Fig. 6b).

The current velocity within the water column reaches a maximum of 7.5 cm/s (Fig. 6c) and is unlikely to be responsible for the observed seismic signals, as it remains lower

267 than the current-induced seismic noise in OBS (Stähler et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2023). The
268 water column heterogeneity shows an increase of about +5% that emerged around 07:00,
269 and continued to rise thereafter, likely resulting from suspended particles, originated from
270 the river discharge. During the discharge, water column heterogeneity exhibits a roughly
271 constant signature from its onset at elevations ≥ 65 m above the lake floor and becomes
272 more pronounced several hours later, particularly at elevations ≥ 30 m above the lake
273 floor (Fig. 6d), likely indicating the presence of an interflow above the thermocline, which is
274 estimated to lie at a depth range of ~ 20 – 30 m from the lake surface (e.g. Bührer & Ambühl,
275 2001). Such an interflow likely led to sediment rain out, contributing to the increased
276 backscatter, as indicated by the water-column heterogeneity observed between 12:00 and
277 14:30 (Fig. 6d). The river discharge onset is broadly aligned with an abrupt shift in the
278 lake’s current direction from $\sim 180^\circ$ to $\sim 90^\circ$ (Fig. 6e), which persists during the discharge,
279 likely indicating the direction of inflow pattern in the lake, characterized by a nearly constant
280 direction and velocity. The eastward flow throughout the entire water column persists for
281 several hours including the time window in which long-period seismic energy is predominant.
282 This sustained eastward flow likely enhanced wave–shore interactions (Fig. 1), potentially
283 contributing to coastal erosion and increased concentrations of suspended particles in the
284 lake, as observed between approximately 16:00 and 00:00 (Fig. 6d).

285 The sub-processes associated with the river discharge that trigger the seismic signal
286 are not yet clearly elucidated. However, the river discharge entering the lake likely carries
287 bedload with momentum (proportional to the inflow velocity), whose temporal variations
288 act as a driving force. The change in momentum can accelerate or decelerate the flow.
289 Depending on the inflow speed, this momentum may have impacted the lake during the
290 inflow–lake interaction, thereby inducing a signal that propagated in the lake. The alignment
291 between the onset of the seismic signal and the sharp increase in river discharge indicates
292 that the seismometer instantaneously records the vibrations induced by the inflow–lake
293 interaction, likely near the river mouth.

Figure 4: Example of a seismic signal driven by river discharge. (a) Precipitation on September 2, 2023, recorded by the weather station in Altdorf, located south of Lake Lucerne. (b) River discharge measured at the hydrological gauging station throughout the day, showing a significant increase around 07:12, which coincided with the onset of the seismic signal. (c) Seismic signal recorded on the vertical component of the ocean bottom seismometer (MUS03), installed near the river mouth. The signal is band-pass filtered between 25 and 120 seconds. (d) Spectrogram of the seismic signal, showing an energy pattern at periods ≥ 25 s. (e) Water column temperature recorded by thermistors. $H(\text{m})$ indicates height above the lakebed, in meters.

Figure 5: Comparison of the power spectral density of the ocean bottom and land-based station, before, during and after the river discharge. (a) OBS vertical component power spectral density within the 00:00–02:00 time window before the river discharge. (b) OBS vertical component power spectral density within the 07:00–12:00 time window, that include the river discharge. (c) OBS vertical component power spectral density within the 21:00–23:00 time window after the river discharge. (d) Power spectral density of the land-based station’s vertical component over the two-hour time window 00:00–02:00, before the river discharge. (e) Power spectral density of the land-based station’s vertical component within the time window 07:00–12:00, during the river discharge. (f) Power spectral density of the land-based station’s vertical component within the time window 21:00–23:00, after the river discharge.

Figure 6: Hydrodynamic measurements on September 22, 2023, the day of the high-discharge event. (a) Lake level (in meters above sea level; i.e., m a.s.l) showing a linear increase on the day of river discharge. (b) Pressure signal recorded by the hydrophone, band-pass filtered between 25 and 120 s, similar to the seismic signal. (c) Current velocity measured by the ADCP. (d) Water column heterogeneity measured by the ADCP, given in percentage (%), and showing an increase around 07:00. (e) The two-dimensional variation of the current direction measured using the ADCP. H(m) denotes the height above the lake floor, in meters.

4.3 Seismic signal induced by foehn-like strong wind

The eastern part of Lake Lucerne is prone to foehn-like strong warm wind (Fig. 7a), with velocity of up to 20 m/s (Fig. 7b). Such strong forcing pushes surface water leeward inducing blowing over the lake's surface level fluctuations and shear induced thermal exchanges. The ocean bottom seismometer deployed on the lakebed recorded a seismic signal (Fig. 7c), with seismic energy increased during the wind event. The signal was isolated by band-pass filtering the raw seismic data (Fig. S6) between 10 and 100 s. The spectrogram of the seismic signal (Fig. 7d) reveals strong energy around 1 s and weak energy at 3 s that persists throughout the day. In contrast, the energy concentrated at ≥ 10 s is more pronounced between $\sim 10:40$ and $20:00$, roughly corresponding to the time window during which the seismic signal exhibits higher amplitude (Fig. 7c). The peak in the seismic signal at 07:12 is well correlated with a sudden change in the lake thermal structure (Fig. 7e), which coincides with a rise in air temperature (Fig. 7a). Such change is the thermal signature of the baroclinic recirculation that is being setup with upwelled and downwelled waters on both end of the basin and strong horizontal currents. The bottom current, which reached ~ 20 cm/s (Fig. S5b), likely generated bottom stress that may have caused the vibration of the OBS and an associated ground displacement on the order of a few micrometers (Fig. 7c).

Unfortunately, the ADCP measurements, particularly the two-dimensional current velocity and its direction, were of poor quality during this event. However, other measurements of moderate quality, such as water column heterogeneity and one-dimensional current velocity are shown on Fig. S5. Wind forcing induced lake-level variations, pressure fluctuations, and current with velocity of ~ 20 cm/s, likely contributing to particle mobilization within the lake (Fig. S5).

The seismic PSDs recorded by the OBS reveals two peaks of high energy centered at 1 s and 10 s respectively and a minimum at 3 s (Fig. 8a). In the short-period band (0.4–2 s), the PSD peak displays a large variability and reaches the high value of -80 dB. It corresponds to the large wind-induced lake microseisms during the foehn episode. At long period (10–100 s), the PSD are also highly variable and above the high noise model. They are related to subprocesses induced by wind within the lake that remain not fully understood.

The land-based station PSDs also display the same two peaks but with much lower amplitudes which remain below the high noise model (Fig. 8b). The variability of the 2 s peak is smaller than for the OBS. The secondary ocean microseisms (SOM) peak at 5 s is clearly visible whereas it is hidden at the OBS by the strong lake induced signals. Finally, in the period band ~ 10 –40 s, the land-based station PSDs display a large variability and amplitudes larger than during quiet days but lower than the OBS station. The hydrophone recorded a signal (Fig. S5b) characterized by a high-energy peak at ~ 1 s (Fig. S4), similar to that observed by the OBS (Fig. 8a). This signal corresponds again to the lake secondary microseisms.

Figure 7: Example of a seismic signal induced by wind forcing, observed in Lake Lucerne on March 29, 2024. (a) Air temperature during the strong wind event. (b) Wind speed measured the meteorological station located in Altdorf (south of the lake). (c) Seismic signal recorded on the vertical component of the ocean bottom seismometer (MUS05), band-pass filtered between 10 and 100 seconds. (d) Spectrogram of the seismic signal, highlighting short-period seismic energy recorded at the lakebed. (e) Two-dimensional spatiotemporal variation of temperature recorded in the water column using thermistors. $H(m)$ denotes the height above the lakebed.

Figure 8: (a) Power spectral density of the seismogram recorded on the vertical component of the OBS (MUS05). Lake microseisms appear between 0.4 and 2 s, while the wind-induced seismic signal is observed between 10 and 100 s. (b) Power spectral density of the seismogram recorded on the vertical component of the land-based seismic station (MUO). The power spectral density was computed for the 24-hour record of 29 March 2024.

4.4 Signal induced by vessel disturbance

Multiple studies have revealed that noise generated by boat traffic in marine settings, such as the ocean, can influence both the behavior and physiology of aquatic species (Vieira et al., 2020; Graham & Cooke, 2008; Rolland et al., 2012). During our experiment in Lake Lucerne, unusual harmonic oscillations were recorded by the OBS. Given their regular occurrence on quiet days (i.e., no other events), we investigated whether passing cruise vessels could be the source. To analyze the signal, we reviewed vessel passage schedules and the Brunnen webcam, and examined pressure and seismic signals for selected days, ensuring that no other lacustrine events (e.g., strong winds or river discharge) occurred. The harmonic oscillations are clearly visible in the seismic and pressure signals (Fig. 9a; Fig. 10a), in their energy (Fig. 9b; Fig. 10b), and in the pressure spectrogram (Fig. 9c; Fig. 10c). These signals were band-pass filtered between 10 and 100 s, guided by the power spectral density analysis (Fig. 10d), which shows significant energy in this range, likely associated with vessel passage near the instrument. As a vessel moves through the water, it generates hydrodynamic processes by displacing fluid and producing pressure fluctuations. The passage also induces acoustic perturbations from machinery and propeller-induced cavitation. These perturbations propagate through the lake, and acoustic–seismic coupling occurs when waves interact with the lakebed, shoreline, or shallow regions, transferring energy into the ground as seismic vibrations. The different peaks observed in the recorded signals are likely related to vessel characteristics and operating conditions, such as size, speed, maneuvering, and distance to the OBS.

Figure 9: (a) Seismic signal induced by vessel disturbance, exhibiting harmonic oscillations. The signal is band-pass filtered between 10 and 100 seconds. (b) Seismic energy, displaying oscillations similar to the signal. (c) Spectrogram of the seismic signal, also showing oscillatory behavior. (d) Image on 2023-10-02, from the webcam installed at Brunnen, with snapshots taken every 10 minutes. (e) Map showing the trajectory of the vessel across the entire lake. The x-axis represents UTC time, while local time corresponds to UTC+2.

Figure 10: (a) Pressure fluctuations induced by vessel disturbance, exhibiting harmonic oscillations. The pressure signal is band-pass filtered between 10 and 100 seconds. (b) Energy of the pressure fluctuations, displaying oscillations similar to the pressure signal. (c) Spectrogram of the pressure signal, also showing oscillatory behavior. (d) Power spectral density (PSD) of the pressure signal, showing high energy up to -110 dB in the period range between 10 and 100 seconds. The x-axis represents UTC time, while local time corresponds to UTC + 2.

Figure 11: Summary of processes generating seismic signals at the lake bottom. (a) Wind-induced lake microseisms, as well as coastal erosion driven by wave orbital motion. Strong winds lead to tilting of the thermocline, causing downwelling and upwelling recirculation. (b) Vessel traffic, oceanic waves, and earthquakes generate seismic signals that are detected at the lake bottom. (c) River discharge transports bedload, and its interaction with the lake is likely to induce seismic signals. The interflow above the thermocline set up sediment rain out, increasing suspended particles in the lake.

5 Discussion

We investigated multiple processes responsible for generating seismic signals within the lake (Fig. 11) and discussed their frequency characteristics and their respective triggering mechanisms. These processes can be broadly classified as short-period (≤ 2 s) and long-period (≥ 10 s). They provide valuable information for near-surface monitoring.

Although the goal of this study is to demonstrate the diversity of environmental processes that can be monitored using ocean bottom seismometers (OBSs), rather than to specifically investigate lake microseisms, our results reveal that wind-driven lake microseisms are clearly observed by both the ocean bottom seismometer and the hydrophone, but are less evident at the land-based station. In this specific case of a narrow, elongated alpine lake such as Lake Lucerne (Uri Basin, i.e., the southernmost part of the lake), the lake geometry likely plays a key role in energy distribution, acting as a waveguide that channels energy preferentially along a south–north axis. Such a geometry influences the lake’s microseismic characteristics, namely its frequency and amplitude (Xu et al., 2017; Carchedi et al., 2022; Besedina et al., 2024). The ocean bottom observations are, however, consistent with the findings of Xu et al. (2017), who investigated lake microseisms using seismic stations surrounding lakes.

Wind stress commonly pushes surface water toward the downwind end of the lake, inducing a horizontal pressure gradient that drives deeper water toward the upwind end. This circulation pattern excites the first vertical internal mode (Münnich et al., 1992), with a period of several hours (Wiegand & Chamberlain, 1987). The observed signal, however, is short-period (< 200 s) compared to the internal mode period and is unlikely to be caused by internal mode-like seiche. Not all high river discharge events induced seismic signals; some discharges characterized by a gradual onset and maximum amplitudes exceeding $80 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ did not produce detectable seismic signals in Lake Lucerne. The generation of a seismic signal by river discharge likely depends on the characteristics of the flow, such as the inflow velocity, onset type (e.g., sharp, flashy, or gradual), amplitude, and bedload content. In this case, a discharge spike with an abrupt and steep onset generated a seismic signal with a correspondingly sharp onset. This signal was likely triggered by vibrational bedload disturbances associated with the rapid inflow of a substantial water mass into the lake system. Although the explanation for the generation of long-period seismic signals is grounded in the physics of environmental processes, the subprocess that directly triggered the signal remains poorly understood, as no available data adequately account for its source in the lake. In the future, the orientation of the OBS may need to be considered in order to attempt to localize certain sources of lacustrine processes. The signals recorded by the ocean bottom seismometers (OBS) are, in some cases, stronger on the horizontal components (Fig. S3) than on the vertical component. This may be due to OBS–lakebed coupling effects or instrument tilt. Although a flat anchor was used to deploy the OBS based on high-resolution bathymetry map (Fig. 1c), uncertainties related to coupling remain. A detailed investigation of the potential effects of instrument tilt and OBS–lakebed coupling, as well as possible correction methods, lies beyond the scope of this study and could be addressed in future work. The signal is more often observed on quiet days, likely due to its weak amplitude compared to other processes (e.g., wind).

396 Integrating seismological observations, weather data, and hydrodynamic measurements
397 represents a key advancement in elucidating seismic signals generated by environmental
398 processes at the lakebed. Extending this multidisciplinary approach to other lakes will
399 yield additional data on similar processes investigated here and provide an opportunity to
400 apply the signal characterization demonstrated in this study to reproduce their frequency
401 characteristics and waveforms. It will also support the expansion of this preliminary catalog
402 with the goal of automating the detection of the processes studied here on a case-by-case
403 basis.

404 **6 Conclusions**

405 We built a preliminary seismic catalog of natural environmental processes observed at
406 the lakebed using non-invasive ocean bottom seismometers (OBSs). The catalog compiles
407 frequency characteristics and representative waveforms of each process, obtained through a
408 multidisciplinary approach that enables the distinction of their seismic signatures.

409 Strong winds, routinely monitored by meteorological services, produce distinct seismic
410 signals at the lakebed, including lake microseisms and long-period oscillations with energy
411 concentrated in two frequency bands: below 2 s and above 10 s. These period bands arise
412 from different physical mechanisms, including nonlinear wave-wave interactions that gen-
413 erate lacustrine secondary microseisms, mechanical vibrations, and wind-driven wave-coast
414 interactions responsible for long-period signals. Wind-forcing dominate the seismic spec-
415 trum recorded by OBSs than the land-based station, thereby obscuring the detection of
416 secondary ocean microseism (SOM) energy at the lake floor.

417 River discharge also generates a clear seismic signature, expressed as strong variability
418 in the power spectral density at periods ≥ 25 s. Unlike wind-forcing, however, river-induced
419 seismic energy is insufficient to mask SOM energy at the lakebed. Lake microseisms exhibit
420 their highest energy in the 0.4–2 s band, and these signals can be exploited to image shallow
421 structures beneath the lakebed. Building such a database will therefore provide improved
422 insight into lake-subsurface properties.

423 OBSs offer distinct advantages over land-based stations for studying environmental
424 processes. Their broadband sensitivity enables monitoring of diverse near-surface pro-
425 cesses at the lake scale, with potential extension to oceanic environments. Positioned at
426 the sediment-water interface, OBSs capture lake microseisms more accurately than land-
427 based stations and detect signals from hydrodynamic forcing, likely sediment transport,
428 and wave-shoreline interactions with greater fidelity. This environmental responsiveness ex-
429 tends the role of OBSs beyond conventional seismology, positioning them as interdisciplinary
430 observational tools capable of recording geophysical, limnological, and climatic signals.

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 437 hydrological stations, making all these data freely available.

438 Data availability

439 The environmental dataset from Swiss Federal Office for the Environment is avail-
 440 able at: <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home.html>. The meteorological data pro-
 441 vide by Swiss meteorological service is available at: [https://www.meteosuisse.admin.ch/
 442 services-et-publications/service/open-data.html](https://www.meteosuisse.admin.ch/services-et-publications/service/open-data.html).

443 The seismological and hydrodynamic data are available upon request. Additional seismic
 444 data: Swiss Seismological Service (SED) at ETH Zurich; (2018): Deployment associated
 445 with OBS deployments in Swiss Lakes; <https://doi.org/10.12686/SED/NETWORKS/XJ>;
 446 Swiss Seismological Service (SED) At ETH Zurich; (1983): National Seismic Networks
 447 of Switzerland; ETH Zürich. Other/Seismic Network; [https://doi.org/10.12686/SED/
 448 NETWORKS/CH](https://doi.org/10.12686/SED/NETWORKS/CH). The photos showing boat traffic on Lake Lucerne are available at [https://
 449 www.foto-webcam.eu/webcam/brunnen/](https://www.foto-webcam.eu/webcam/brunnen/).

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543 **Supporting Information for A Multidisciplinary Approach to Linking**
544 **Seismological Observations and Environmental Processes**

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556 This supplementary section provides additional material on the seismic signals recorded
557 across all three components of the ocean bottom seismometer (OBS) during the environ-
558 mental events analyzed in the manuscript. To complement the main discussion, we include
559 additional analyses of the OBSs highlighting differences their sensitivity to lake-related pro-
560 cesses.

561 The vertical component spectra are examined alongside pressure records to illustrate
562 how wind forcing influences both seismic and hydrodynamic responses. During a represen-
563 tative windy day, the OBS captures pronounced lake microseisms, whereas the land-based
564 station shows weaker or absent signatures. The supplementary figures further demonstrate
565 spectral peaks near ~ 1 s (Fig. S4) and enhanced energy at periods ≥ 10 s in the pressure
566 data, features consistent with wind-driven processes. These comparisons underscore the
567 distinct observational capabilities of OBSs relative to land-based sensors.

568 All supplementary figures referenced here are directly linked to the results presented in
569 the manuscript.

Figure S1: Example of the Mw 7.5 earthquake that occurred in Japan on January 1, 2024, and observed in Lake Lucerne during the experiment. (a) Seismic waveform recorded on the vertical component of the OBS (MUS05). (b) Power spectral density (PSD) of the seismogram recorded on the vertical component over a day. (c) Current velocity measured by the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP). (d) Water column heterogeneity, measured by the ADCP, and reflecting the spatial distribution of suspended particles throughout the column. (e) Flow direction in the lake, measured by the ADCP, provides insight into the spatial and temporal variability of near-surface and subsurface currents. (f) Water column temperature, continuously recorded by thermistors over a 24-hour period. H(m) denotes height above the lakebed, given in meters.

Figure S2: Example of a relatively calm day with no specific event. (a) Wind speed with a maximum value below 3 m/s. (b) Weak river discharge showing a minor peak around 15:30. (c) Seismic signal recorded on the vertical component of OBS, MUS08, on 13 January 2024, representative of seismic noise. (d) Spectrogram of the vertical component of the OBS signal, highlighting a constant energy (-135 dB) between 3–7 s throughout the day, associated with ocean microseisms.

Figure S3: Raw seismic signals recorded on the three components of OBS MUS03 during the high discharge on 22 September 2023. (a) HH2 component represents a non-oriented horizontal. (b) Non-oriented horizontal component (HH1). (c) HHZ represents the vertical component.

Figure S4: Power spectral density of the pressure signal recorded by the hydrophone during the strong wind event on 29 March 2024. The peak at ~ 1 s is similar to the lake-microseism peak observed in the OBS seismic data.

Figure S5: (a) Lake level recorded during the strong-wind event. (b) Pressure signal recorded by the hydrophone. (c) Current velocity recorded by the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP). (d) Two-dimensional backscatter anomaly (%), highlighting water-column heterogeneity. H (m) denotes height above the lakebed.

Figure S6: Raw seismic signals recorded on the three components of OBS MUS05 during a strong wind on 29 March 2024: (a) HH2 component represents a non-oriented horizontal. (b) Non-oriented horizontal component (HH3). (c) Vertical component.

Figure S7: (a) Seismic signal induced by vessel disturbance on 2023-10-01, exhibiting harmonic oscillations. The signal is band-pass filtered between 10 and 100 seconds. (b) Seismic energy, displaying oscillations similar to the signal. (c) Spectrogram of the seismic signal, also showing oscillatory behavior. (d) Image on 2023-10-01, from the webcam installed at Brunnen, with snapshots taken every 10 minutes. (e) Map showing the trajectory of the vessel across the entire lake. The x-axis represents UTC time, while local time corresponds to UTC+2.

Figure S8: (a) Pressure fluctuations induced by vessel disturbance on 2023-10-01, exhibiting harmonic oscillations. The pressure signal is band-pass filtered between 10 and 100 seconds. (b) Energy of the pressure fluctuations, displaying oscillations similar to the pressure signal. (c) Spectrogram of the pressure signal, also showing oscillatory behavior. (d) Power spectral density (PSD) of the pressure signal, showing high energy up to -110 dB in the period range between 10 and 100 seconds. The x-axis represents UTC time, while local time corresponds to UTC + 2.